

DETERMINATION OF QUALITY INDICATORS OF APPLE, BEET, CARROTS, AND PUMPKIN POWDER

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Abstract. *The given article determines the quality indicators of apple, beet, carrot, and pumpkin powders. These powders, prepared from local raw materials, are not only important for the food industry, but also their health benefits are one of the pressing issues. The study investigated the organoleptic, chemical, and physical properties of the raw materials, as well as their moisture content, acidity, preservation of nutrients, and overall biological value.*

It has been established that apple powder contains a high percentage of ascorbic acid and natural antioxidants, while beet powder contains betalain and mineral substances. The composition of carrot and pumpkin powders is characterized by a rich content of carotenes and tissue restorants. The research results demonstrate the possibility of using these powders as a functional additive in food products.

The obtained data will serve as a scientific basis for the further introduction of these powders into technological processes, increasing their production volumes, and meeting consumer demand. Therefore, the research findings contribute to increasing economic efficiency and developing the production of healthy food products.

Keywords: *apple powder, beet powder, carrot powder, pumpkin powder, quality indicators, organoleptic properties, biological value, functional food, nutrients, technological processes*

Introduction: At present time it is important to suggest that the demand for functional food products is increasing, which is associated with the desire for a healthy lifestyle and increased interest in products made from natural raw materials. Vegetables and fruits, such as apples, beets, carrots and pumpkins, are rich in vitamins, minerals and antioxidants important for human health, and their powders are widely used in the food industry [1].

The purpose of the study was to determine the quality indicators of powders made from these products. The relevance of the study is that these powders not only serve as essential raw materials for the production of healthy food, but also contribute to the local economy by optimizing production processes [2].

Definitely, powders from apples, beets, carrots and pumpkins enhance the taste, color and biological value of food products, extend their shelf life. The results of these studies, in particular information on the preservation of nutrients in the product and the possibilities of their use in technological processes, serve as an important scientific basis for the production of healthy and environmentally friendly products. [3]

Methods and research techniques. Dry substances (moisture) SOST 28561-90 [4], SOST 5900-14, SOST 21094-75, soluble dry substances SOST 2173-13, acidity by titration SOST ISO 750-13, SOST 5670-96, active acidity [5] SOST 26188-16, total sugar content SOST 8756.13-87, SOST 5903-89, SOST 5672-68, protein content according to the Kjeldahl method SOST 26889-

86, fat content SOST 8756.21-89, SOST 31902-12, SOST 5668-68, ash content SOST 25555.4-91, SOST 15113.8-77, SOST 5901-14, I.K.

According to the Merry method, beta-carotene content is extracted with acetone according to SOST 8756.22-80 [6] and separated on a sorption column with aluminum oxide to separate it from petroleum ether and other pigments measured by length [7].

Results and discussion. In order to substantiate the possibility of using fruit and vegetable powders in food production, it was considered appropriate to determine their consumer characteristics [8]. Analysis of the organoleptic quality indicators of apple, beetroot, carrot and pumpkin powders showed that all the test samples are the same, liquid, in the form of a powdery substance with the color, taste and smell characteristic of the original raw materials. The powders under study have the following colors: apple powder: yellow-brown; beetroot powder: brown-red; carrot powder: brown-orange; pumpkin powder: yellow-orange.

Based on the results of the assessment of the physicochemical quality indicators:

- the particle size of apple, beetroot, carrot and pumpkin powder does not exceed 200 microns;
- the powders are restored in water within 10 minutes;
- the content of sand and metal impurities in 1 kg of dried powder is less than 0.01% and less than 0.0003%, respectively. Foreign impurities were not detected.

Tables 1 and 2 present the results of studies on the content of carbohydrates, antioxidants, minerals and nutritional value of powders from apples, beets, carrots and pumpkin.

Table 1.

Number of carbohydrates in fruit and vegetable powders (per 100 g of product)

Semi-finished products	QM, g	Mono- and disaccharides		QM, g		
		monosaccharides	disaccharides	water-soluble pectins	protopectins	fiber
Apple powder	92,3	38,2	7,5	5,2	7,3	10,0
Beetroot powder	92,4	2,0	46,1	2,5	10,7	7,5
Carrot powder	92,2	20,7	25,0	2,3	9,3	9,3
Pumpkin powder	92,3	35,3	11,7	2,9	7,8	15,9

According to the data presented in Table 1, carbohydrates in apple, beetroot, carrot and pumpkin powders are represented by monosaccharides, disaccharides and polysaccharides. Monosaccharides contain reducing sugars such as fructose and glucose. Disaccharides are found mainly in the form of sucrose.

The percentage content of mono- and disaccharides in apple, beetroot, carrot and pumpkin powders is distributed as follows: Apple: 84% monosaccharides, 16% disaccharides; beetroot: 4% monosaccharides, 96% disaccharides; carrot: 45% monosaccharides, 55% disaccharides; pumpkin: 75% monosaccharides, 25% disaccharides.

The studies have shown that reducing sugars predominate in powders obtained from apple and beet pulp. The amount of structural carbohydrates, including fiber and pectin, was determined in fruit and vegetable powders. According to the SOST R 54059-2010 standard, dietary fiber belongs to categories A, B, G, D, DE and has the following effects: Supports metabolism; Preserves teeth and bone tissue; Improves the functioning of the immune system, gastrointestinal

system and cardiovascular system. In Russia, the average daily requirement for dietary fiber for adults is 20 g, and for children over 3 years old - 10-20 g.

According to table 3.5.2.2, dietary fiber in 100 g of powder is: Apple: 22.5 g - 112.5% of the daily requirement for adults; Beetroot: 20.7 g - 103.5% of the daily requirement for adults; Carrot: 20.9 g - 104.5% of the daily requirement for adults; Pumpkin: 58.9 g - 294.5% of the daily requirement for adults. The content of antioxidants in the powders was determined, including: SAF index (free radical activity); Ascorbic acid; flavonoids; The content of beta-carotene was analyzed.

Table 2.

Number of antioxidants in fruit and vegetable powders (per 100 g of product)

Semi-finished products	SAF, mg	Vitamins, mg		Flavonoids, mg		
		S	carotene	catechin	anthocyanin	flavonol
Apple powder	230,4	117,2	1,2	55,7	8,6	389,2
Beetroot powder	416,3	82,5	0,4	58,9	106,5	1126,7
Carrot powder	120,8	33,2	25,0	22,5	5,0	92,7
Pumpkin powder	97,7	37,2	23,2	31,6	7,8	84,2

According to SOST R 54059-2010, vitamin C is included in the functional ingredients of categories A, B, B, D and DE and has the following effects: Support of metabolic processes; antioxidant protection; Maintenance of the cardiovascular system; Support of the immune system; Strengthening of teeth and bone tissue.

The antioxidant effect of vitamin C, flavonoids and beta-carotene is explained by their ability to protect against free radicals. Such protection ensures the following: preservation of polyunsaturated fatty acids in membrane lipids; Protection of the structure and functional activity of DNA; Preservation of the structure and function of protein.

Vitamin C helps stabilize blood sugar levels, provides antioxidant protection of cell membranes and lipid lipoproteins, supports the synthesis of connective tissue, which makes up the main framework of bone tissue, and promotes general immunomodulation. In Uzbekistan, the daily requirement of vitamin C for adults is 90 mg, and for children - 30-90 mg. According to table 3.5.2.2: 100 g of apple, beetroot, carrot and pumpkin powder contain vitamin C in the following amounts: apple: 130.2% of the daily value; beetroot: 91.7%; carrot: 36.9%; pumpkin: 41.3%.

Beta-carotene makes the human body resistant to some types of cancer, including breast cancer, maintains the structure and activity of proteins, and has an anti-sclerotic effect. In Uzbekistan, the physiological need for beta-carotene for adults is 5 mg / day. Beta-carotene consumption in different countries averages 1.8-5.0 mg / g.

Among the powders studied, apple and beet powders are characterized by a low content of beta-carotene, while carrot and pumpkin powders have a high content of this antioxidant. To meet 100% of the daily need for beta-carotene in adults, an average of 20 g of carrot or pumpkin powder is needed.

Flavonoids help stimulate metabolism and lipolysis, play an important role in maintaining the tone of vascular walls, improving their permeability, nutrition and blood supply to the heart muscle. They exhibit the following effects: Antithrombotic; Vasodilator; Antiarrhythmic.

The number of flavonols, catechins and anthocyanins was determined in the remains of apples, beets, carrots and pumpkins. In Uzbekistan, the daily requirement for flavonoids for adults is 250 mg, for children aged 7–18 years – 150–250 mg.

The number of flavonoids in 100 g of apple, beetroot, carrot and pumpkin powder ranges from 120.2 mg to 1292.1 mg. The amount of powder required to meet 100% of the daily requirement for flavonoids: apple powder: 55.1 g; beetroot powder: 19.3 g; carrot powder: 208.0 g; pumpkin powder: 55.1 g.

Table 3.

Amount of macro- and microelements in fruit and vegetable powders (per 100 g).

Semi-finished products	Minerals, gm								
	Ash,g	Ca	K	Mg	P	Fe	Cu	Zn	Mn
Apple powder	3,0	253,0	126,5	122,5	113,5	8,73	0,40	0,30	0,20
Beet flour	6,9	270,1	226,4	157,6	233,2	5,45	0,34	1,82	0,83
Carrot powder	6,1	463,0	401,3	342,3	579,9	2,18	0,22	0,66	0,44
Pumpkin powder	3,3	199,3	354,6	108,3	129,4	1,50	0,42	0,47	0,14

The macronutrient calcium plays an important role in maintaining the condition of tooth enamel, forming and maintaining bone mineral density, and preventing the absorption of undissolved proteins. In Russia, the daily requirement for calcium for adults is 1000 mg, for children – 400–1200 mg, for people over 60 – 1200 mg.

According to Table 3, 100 g of apple, beetroot, carrot, and pumpkin powders satisfy the daily requirement for calcium as follows: apple – 25.3%; beetroot – 27.0%; carrot – 46.3%; pumpkin – 19.9%.

Phosphorus and magnesium, like calcium, help reduce the risk of osteoporosis. In Russia, the daily requirement for phosphorus for adults is 800 mg, and for children – 300–1200 mg. Phosphorus in 100 g of powder satisfies the daily requirement: apple - 14.2%, beetroot - 29.2%; carrot - 72.5%; pumpkin - 16.2%.

The daily requirement for magnesium is 400 mg for adults and 55-400 mg for children. The level of satisfaction of the daily requirement for magnesium in 100 g of powder: apple - 30.6%; beetroot - 39.4%; carrot - 85.6%; pumpkin - 27.1%.

The daily requirement for potassium is 2500 mg for adults and 400-2500 mg for children. The daily requirement for potassium in 100 g of powder: apple - 5.1%; beetroot - 9.1%; carrot - 16.1%; pumpkin - 14.2%.

The trace element zinc makes the body resistant to the risk of prostate cancer, provides cell membranes and lipoproteins with antioxidant protection. In Russia, the daily requirement for zinc for adults is 12 mg, for children 3-12 mg. The daily requirement for zinc in 100 g of powder: apple - 2.5%; beetroot - 15.2%; carrot - 5.5%; pumpkin - 3.9%.

Certainly, honey and manganese support the synthesis of connective tissue that forms bone tissue. In Russia, the daily requirement for copper is 1 mg, manganese - 2 mg. The level of

satisfaction of daily honey requirement in 100 g of powder: apple - 40%; beetroot - 34%; carrot - 22%; pumpkin - 42%.

According to the data in table 4, the energy value of apple, beetroot, carrot and pumpkin powders is at the level of 1173.2-1193.7 kJ (280.4-285.3 kcal), which is mainly due to their digestibility, determined by carbohydrates.

Table 4.

Nutritional value of fruit and vegetable powders (per 100 g).

Indicators	Powder			
	Apple	Beetroot	Carrot	Pumpkin
Carbohydrates, g	54,8	55,5	59,7	55,6
Organic acids (Malic acid)	3,5	-		
Fats, g	5,5	-		
Protein	3,0	9,3	5,5	6,8
Energy value, kDj (kcal)	1173,2 (280,4)	1193,7 (285,3)	1089,1 (260,3)	1041,4 (248,9)

According to the results of the studies of the chemical composition of apple, beetroot, carrot and pumpkin powders, it can be noted that these semi-finished products are a source of dietary fiber and antioxidants (vitamin C, beta-carotene and flavonoids). Therefore, they can be recommended for the creation of new types of food products with high nutritional value, including for the production of healthy and functional products. The safety of apple, beetroot, carrot and pumpkin powders was assessed by determining the number of toxic elements and pesticides in them. Also: apple powders were tested for the presence of the mycotoxin patulin; The number of nitrates in carrot and beet powder was assessed; The presence of radionuclides in plant powders was detected.

Summary. In conclusion it should be suggested that the results of the studies of the quality indicators of apple, beetroot, carrot and pumpkin powders show that these products have great potential for creating healthy and functional products in the food industry. The organoleptic properties, physicochemical indicators, carbohydrate, antioxidant and mineral composition of these powders were studied in detail. The high nutritional value of the studied powders is explained by the presence of carbohydrates (monosaccharides and disaccharides), dietary fiber (pectins and cellulose) and antioxidants (vitamin C, beta-carotene and flavonoids). These components help maintain metabolism, strengthen the immune system and improve the functioning of the cardiovascular system.

An assessment of the mineral content showed that the powders are a good source of calcium, magnesium, phosphorus and potassium, which are important for strengthening bone tissue and maintaining the overall functioning of the body. At the same time, the presence of trace elements such as zinc, copper and manganese also expand the possibilities of using these products in creating healthy food products.

Additionally, the safety parameters of the powders were analyzed and it was found that toxic elements, pesticides, mycotoxins and nitrates are at the standard level. Besides that, the powders are quickly restored in water and do not contain foreign impurities, which makes it convenient to introduce them into technological processes.

With high nutritional and energy value, these powders not only meet the requirements of healthy nutrition, but can also find wide application in the production of new types of products,

including sweets, drinks and other functional foods. It was noted that apple, beetroot, carrot and pumpkin powders are not only natural ingredients with high nutritional value, but also an important resource for the production of innovative products that increase economic efficiency based on local raw materials. The results of these studies serve as a scientific basis for the development of the food industry and healthy nutrition.

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